

Prevalent Errors in Senior Secondary School Science Practical as Perceived by Science Teachers in Ekiti State, Nigeria

AUTHOR(S): JEGEDE Samuel Akingbade (Ph.D)
AND
OTOIDE Titilayo Folayemi

Abstract

The study identified prevalent errors in science practical as perceived by science teachers in senior secondary schools using descriptive research of the survey type. The participants were 243 science teachers selected from Ekiti State public senior secondary schools, through multi-stage sampling procedure. An instrument titled Perceived Prevalent Errors Questionnaire (PPEQ) was used to collect data from science teachers across the three senatorial districts of Ekiti State. The data collected were collated and analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics involving frequency counts, percentages and Analysis of Variance. The results of the study revealed among others that Personal errors, Instrumental errors, Observation errors, Systematic errors, Random errors, Calculation errors, Graph errors, errors in Drawing and Gender related Errors were perceived as prevalent errors during science practical in senior secondary schools while Environmental errors appeared to be less prevalent across the three core-fields of science. The results further revealed that errors in science practical were most prevalent in physics. It was therefore recommended among others, that science teachers should ensure that sufficient time for practical classes is accommodated on the school time table on weekly basis and that more attention is paid to the individual student in the practical classes so as to help them develop interest in the mastery of science practical content which could help to reduce errors during practical and ensure accuracy of results of laboratory experiments in science.

IJARBAS

Accepted 10 June 2021
Published 22 June 2021
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5015307

Keywords: Science Practical, Prevalence, Errors, Accuracy,

About Author

Author(s):

JEGEDE Samuel Akingbade (Ph.D)
Department of Science Education, Faculty of Education,
Ekiti State University, Ado-Ekiti, Ekiti State, Nigeria.
canonsamakjeg@yahoo.com

And

OTOIDE Titilayo Folayemi
otoideotoide33@gmail.com

Introduction

Science is an inquiry oriented discipline to which practical work is very essential. According to Aina and Ayodele (2018), science education involves the teaching and learning of scientific knowledge with the purpose of sharing the knowledge with the society for sustainable development. The interplay between the process and product of science is what gives technology what it requires to provide for the daily needs of every individual. This implies that human existence is actually dependent mainly on science. This is in line with the submission of Bak (2010), that science has become more deeply embedded in our everyday life. This could be one of the reasons why it is generally believed that science makes life facilitating, interesting and comfortable to man. Ogunleye and Adepeju (2011) as well as Gracy (2016) concurred to the fact that science as a whole, shape the way we understand the universe, the planet, ourselves and other living things around us.

The importance of science to the advancement of a nation's technology cannot be overemphasized. Everything in the universe is a product of science hence the world is science. Physics, chemistry and biology are the three core fields of science that are being taught in Senior Secondary Schools. They are compulsory subjects that must be passed at credit level for any student who wished to pursue a career in science and technological fields in tertiary institutions. The importance of science to technological advancement has made it a practical oriented subject. Hence the importance of practical activities to the teaching and learning of science cannot be overemphasized. This is supported by Nzewi (2008) that active involvement of students in practical activities will give rise to more effective learning. Also, Liswaniso (2019) affirmed that complementing science teaching with practical activities helps learners to understand the contents well. The submissions of Nzewi and Liswaniso might not be far from the truth as investigations from several examiners across the country confirmed that the majority of students who usually failed science subjects in senior secondary school certificate examinations are those that are unable to accurately carryout experiments during the practical aspect of the examinations. In other word, students that are successful in the practical aspect will only need to put little efforts during the theoretical aspect of the examinations to get the needed grades that will qualify them for higher studies.

Errors are mistakes or omissions made during practical activities. Owolabi (2013) asserted that students commit errors which usually rendered their works useless because they do not pay good attention to vital areas of science practical. Errors could be personal due to imperfection of students' sense organs, parallax errors in reading of meter rule, students' inability to read accurately the meniscus of liquid in a measuring cylinder, making mistakes during dilutions, spilling chemicals during transfer, forgetting to check up whether the apparatus are in good condition or not, breaking of apparatus as a result of fear and examination consciousness among others. They could also be systematic errors because the student does not know how to use the apparatus properly. Errors could also be random because the power of concentration of the student is fading (Boundless, 2016). Observational errors such as inappropriate recording of observation or reliance solely on single reading in an experiment among others can also occur during practical activities in science. In addition, some researchers confirmed that students' performance in science varied with gender (Aniodoh & Egbo, 2013; Ajayi, 2016; Olu-Ajayi 2017; Azman, et al., 2018). Hence, errors can also occur based on students' gender.

The knowledge of science is required in the production of man's basic needs such as food, drugs, cotton and building materials. Emmanuel (2013) affirmed that science education is the vehicle that conveyed scientific knowledge and skills to the people who are in need of

capacities and potentials for developing. Hence the need for its learning through effective practical activities that is devoid of errors. However, despite its important role in the advancement of the society, it appears that there is lack of awareness of the importance of science practical activities with little or no errors. Errors appear to have been on the increase in almost all practical activities in science. In view of this, the research was carried out to investigate the prevalence of errors in science practical as perceived by teachers in senior secondary schools.

The purpose of the study was to investigate the errors that are prevalent in science practical activities in senior secondary schools and to find out in which of the three core fields of science (Physics, Chemistry and Biology) are errors most prevalent during practical activities.

Research Questions

Two research questions were raised for the study. They are:

1. What are the common errors committed by students during science practical as perceived by teachers?
2. In which of the three core fields of science (Physics, Chemistry and Biology) are errors most prevalent?

Research Hypothesis

One null hypothesis was postulated to guide the study and was tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant difference in the perception of male and female science teachers about the errors committed by students in physics, chemistry and biology practical.

Methodology

This research employed a descriptive research of the survey type. Descriptive survey research design is a procedure whereby a unit of the population is studied in details so as to generalise the result on the entire population. The population for this study comprised all the 1,563 teachers teaching physics, chemistry and biology in public senior secondary schools in Ekiti State, Nigeria as at the time of investigation. (Source: Ekiti State Teaching Service Commission). A sample of 243 senior secondary school science teachers was drawn from nine local government areas across the three senatorial districts of Ekiti State. The sample was selected using multi-stage sampling procedure. At the first stage, three local government areas were selected from each of the senatorial districts using simple random sampling by balloting. The second stage involved the selection of senior secondary school science teachers across the selected three local government areas in each of the senatorial districts using stratified random sampling technique where subject (physics, chemistry and biology) was used as stratification variable. Consequently, 81 teachers which comprised 27 physics teachers, 27 chemistry teachers and 27 biology teachers were randomly selected from each of the senatorial districts, making a total of 243 teachers across the three senatorial districts.

A questionnaire tagged "Perceived Prevalent Errors Questionnaire (PPEQ)" was the only instrument used for the study. The instrument was developed to measure the prevalent errors in science practical activities. The instrument consists of two sections A and B. Section A consists of the respondents' bio-data and preliminary information for science teachers while section B consists of a 40- item statements used to elicit information on the perceived prevalent errors in science practical. The responses were scored as follows: Very Prevalent (VP) – 4 points; Prevalent (P) – 3 points; Slightly Prevalent (SP) – 2 points; Not Prevalent (NP) – 1 point. The face and content validity of the instrument were ascertained by experts in the

field of Science Education, Test, Measurement and Evaluation. A reliability coefficient of 0.91 was obtained through split half method.

The data collected were collated and analysed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The questions raised were answered using descriptive statistics involving frequency counts and percentages while the hypothesis postulated was tested using Analysis of Variance. Decision was taken at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Research Question 1: What are the common errors committed by students during science practical as perceived by teachers?

In order to answer the question, the items on the questionnaire were grouped into 10 forms of errors. Respondents' scores were categorized into two – Below 50% and above 50% of the total score on each of the errors in science practical. Scores equal to or above 50% of the total score were considered as being common errors in science practical. The result is presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Common errors committed by students during chemistry practical as perceived by teachers

Errors Committed	Below 50%	50% and above	Ranking
Personal Errors	51(21.0)	192(79.0)*	2 nd
Environmental Errors	130(53.5)	113(46.5)	10 th
Instrumental Errors	47(19.3)	196(80.7)*	1 st
Observation Errors	51(21.8)	182(78.2)*	3 rd
Systematic Errors	64(26.3)	179(73.7)*	4 th
Random Errors	74(30.5)	169(69.5)*	5 th
Calculation Errors	79(32.5)	164(67.5)*	7 th
Graph Errors	75(30.9)	168(69.1)*	6 th
Errors in Drawing	85(35.0)	158(65.0S)*	8 th
Gender related Errors	112(46.1)	131(53.9)*	9 th

* = Common errors, Percentage responses are enclosed in parentheses

Using a cut-off point of 50% and above, the result reveals that all the errors are commonly committed by students during science practical except environmental errors. Ranking of common errors committed by students during science practical indicates that instrumental errors are the most common errors committed by students during science practical. This is closely followed by personal errors, observation errors, systematic errors, random errors, graphs errors, calculation errors, error in drawing and gender related errors, while environmental errors is the least in the ranking order.

Research Question 2: In which of the three core fields of science (Physics, Chemistry and Biology) are errors most prevalent?

In answering the question, respondents' scores in each of the three core fields were categorized into two – Below 50% and above 50% of the total score on each of the errors in science practical. Scores equal to or above 50% of the total score were considered as being

prevalent errors in each of the core fields of science practical. The result is presented in Table 2

Table 2: Error prevalence in the three core fields of science

Errors Committed	Physics		Chemistry		Biology	
	Below 50%	50% and above	Below 50%	50% and above	Below 50%	50% and above
Personal Errors	17(21.0)	64(79.0)*	9(11.1)	72(88.9)*	17(21.0)	64(79.0)*
Environmental Errors	46(56.8)	35(43.2)	54(66.6)	27(33.3)	32(39.5)	49(60.5)*
Instrumental Errors	11(13.0)	70(87.0)*	23(28.7)	58(71.3)*	13(15.8)	68(84.2)*
Observation Errors	16(19.5)	65(80.5)*	18(22.5)	63(77.5)*	19(23.7)	62(76.3)*
Systematic Errors	20(24.7)	61(75.3)*	16(19.8)	65(80.2)*	31(39.5)	42(58.0)*
Random Error	15(18.2)	66(81.8)*	17(21.0)	64(79.0)*	41(50.6)	40(49.4)
Calculation error	22(27.3)	59(72.7)*	11(13.6)	70(86.4)*	47(58.0)	34(42.0)
Graph Errors	17(21.0)	64(79.0)*	21(26.0)	60(74.0)*	36(44.4)	45(55.6)*
Errors in Drawing	28(34.6)	53(65.4)*	20(24.7)	61(75.3)*	34(42.0)	50(60.5)*
Gender related Errors	28(34.6)	53(65.4)*	41(50.6)	40(49.4)	40(49.4)	41(50.6)*
Average	22(27.2)	59(72.8)	23(28.4)	58(71.6)	31(38.3)	50(61.7)

* = Prevalent errors, Percentage responses are enclosed in parentheses

Table 2 presents the errors that are prevalent during science practical as perceived by teachers. The result reveals that all the errors are prevalent during Physics practical except environmental errors. In Chemistry practical, errors such as personal, instrumental, observation, systematic, random, calculation, graph and drawing errors are prevalent except environmental and gender related errors. As regards Biology practical, nearly all the errors are prevalent except random and calculation errors. In general, errors that are prevalent across the three subjects as perceived by teachers include personal errors, instrumental errors, observation errors, systematic errors, graph errors and errors in drawing. However, errors in science practical are most prevalent in Physics.

Hypothesis Testing: There is no significant difference in the perception of male and female science teachers about the errors committed by students in physics, chemistry and biology practical.

In testing this hypothesis, Scores on errors committed by students and mean scores of male and female science teachers were compared for statistical significance in Physics, Chemistry and Biology practical using Analysis of variance (ANOVA) at 0.05 level of significance. The result is presented in Table 3, 4, 5 and 6

Table 3: 2 X 3 ANOVA showing perception of errors committed by students in Physics, Chemistry and Biology practical by gender and subjects

Errors	Source	SS	Df	MS	F	P
Personal	Corrected Model	450.340	5	90.068	5.794	.000
	Sex	215.944	1	215.944	13.892*	.000
	Subject	256.582	2	128.291	8.253*	.000
	Sex * Subject	242.763	2	121.382	7.809*	.001
	Error	3683.956	237	15.544		
	Total	62190.000	243			
	Corrected Total	4134.296	242			
Environmental	Corrected Model	514.806	5	102.961	15.230	.000
	Sex	300.683	1	300.683	44.477*	.000
	Subject	225.995	2	112.997	16.715*	.000
	Sex * Subject	330.129	2	165.065	24.416*	.000
	Error	1602.215	237	6.760		
	Total	15480.000	243			
	Corrected Total	2117.021	242			
Instrumental	Corrected Model	209.018	5	41.804	7.551	.000
	Sex	134.923	1	134.923	24.370*	.000
	Subject	115.620	2	57.810	10.442*	.000
	Sex * Subject	81.394	2	40.697	7.351*	.001
	Error	1312.126	237	5.536		
	Total	16066.000	243			
	Corrected Total	1521.144	242			

*p<0.05

Table 4: 2 X 3 ANOVA showing perception of errors committed by students in physics, chemistry and biology practical by gender and subjects (CONTD)

Errors	Source	SS	Df	MS	F	P
Observation	Corrected Model	225.430	5	45.086	10.157	.000
	Sex	103.154	1	103.154	23.238*	.000
	Subject	60.620	2	30.310	6.828*	.001
	Sex * Subject	170.818	2	85.409	19.240*	.000
	Error	1052.059	237	4.439		

Errors	Source	SS	Df	MS	F	P
	Total	15210.000	243			
	Corrected Total	1277.490	242			
Systematic	Corrected Model	176.560	5	35.312	16.784	.000
	SEX	80.942	1	80.942	38.472*	.000
	Subject	3.298	2	1.649	.784	.458
	Sex * Subject	89.727	2	44.863	21.324*	.000
	Error	498.625	237	2.104		
	Total	6165.000	243			
	Corrected Total	675.185	242			
Random	Corrected Model	205.508	5	41.102	15.466	.000
	SEX	83.748	1	83.748	31.514*	.000
	Subject	.546	2	.273	.103	.902
	Sex * Subject	83.128	2	41.564	15.640*	.000
	Error	629.834	237	2.658		
	Total	5924.000	243			
	Corrected Total	835.342	242			

*p<0.05

Table 5: 2 X 3 ANOVA showing perception of errors committed by students in physics, chemistry and biology practical by gender and subjects (CONTD)

Errors	Source	SS	Df	MS	F	P
Calculation	Corrected Model	2293.755	5	458.751	21.887	.000
	Sex	1256.860	1	1256.860	59.966*	.000
	Subject	66.740	2	33.370	1.592	.206
	Sex * Subject	860.318	2	430.159	20.523*	.000
	Error	4967.431	237	20.960		
	Total	70143.000	243			
	Corrected Total	7261.185	242			
Graph	Corrected Model	1070.912	5	214.182	5.766	.000
	Sex	539.418	1	539.418	14.521*	.000
	Subject	223.905	2	111.953	3.014	.051

Errors	Source	SS	Df	MS	F	P
	Sex * Subject	741.905	2	370.953	9.986*	.000
	Error	8803.813	237	37.147		
	Total	93134.000	243			
	Corrected Total	9874.724	242			
Drawing	Corrected Model	211.734	5	42.347	7.564*	.000
	Sex	15.284	1	15.284	2.730	.100
	Subject	40.669	2	20.334	3.632*	.028
	Sex * Subject	77.535	2	38.767	6.925	.001
	Error	1326.768	237	5.598		
	Total	13600.000	243			
	Corrected Total	1538.502	242			

*p<0.05

Table 6: 2 X 3 ANOVA showing perception of errors committed by students in physics, chemistry and biology practical by gender and subjects (CONTD)

Errors	Source	SS	Df	MS	F	P
Gender related	Corrected Model	125.789	5	25.158	10.651	.000
	Sex	39.775	1	39.775	16.839*	.000
	Subject	26.639	2	13.319	5.639*	.004
	Sex * Subject	100.207	2	50.103	21.212*	.000
	Error	559.800	237	2.362		
	Total	4494.000	243			
	Corrected Total	685.588	242			

*p<0.05

Table 3, 4, 5 and 6 revealed that there is significant difference in the perception of Personal errors ($F_{2,237}=8.253$, $p<0.05$), Environmental errors ($F_{2,237}=24.416$, $p<0.05$), Instrumental errors ($F_{2,237}=7.351$, $p<0.05$), Observation errors ($F_{2,237}=19.240$, $p<0.05$), Systematic errors ($F_{2,237}=21.324$, $p<0.05$), Random errors ($F_{2,237}=15.640$, $p<0.05$), Calculation errors ($F_{2,237}=20.523$, $p<0.05$), Graph errors ($F_{2,237}=9.986$, $p<0.05$), errors in Drawing ($F_{2,237}=6.925$, $p<0.05$) and Gender related errors ($F_{2,237}=21.212$, $p<0.05$) committed by

students in Physics, Chemistry and Biology practical by male and female science teachers at 0.05 level of significance in each case.

Discussion

The study showed that personal errors, instrumental errors, observation errors, systematic errors, random errors, calculation errors, graph errors, errors in drawing and gender related errors were prevalent errors during science practical. This is an indication that errors do actually occur during science practical activities. This is in line with the submission of Allchin (2000) that errors cannot but occur in science practical. In the same vein, Owolabi (2003) agreed that it is almost impossible to obtain a result in science practical which is absolutely free from error.

Ranking of common errors committed by students during science practical indicates that instrumental errors were the most prevalent errors committed by students during science practical. This is not unexpected as most of the instruments for science practical activities in schools are grossly inadequate (Aina, 2013; Arokoyu & Charles-Ogan, 2017). The instrumental errors were closely followed by Personal errors, Observation errors, Systematic errors, Random errors, Calculation errors, Graphs errors, Errors in drawing and Gender related errors while Environmental errors are the least in the ranking order. This could be part of the reasons why Owolabi (2007) affirmed that errors can be traced to how apparatus are being handled, the method of observing and recording among others. In corroboration with Owolabi's affirmation, majority of the science teachers attested that most of the students do commit personal errors such as psychological problem as a result of phobia, inability to read accurately the meniscus of liquid in a measuring cylinder, forgetting to check up whether apparatus are in good condition or complete, breaking of apparatus as a result of fear and examination consciousness among others.

The study showed that errors in science practical were most prevalent in Physics. Analysis of the errors committed by students on subject basis showed that all the errors except environmental errors were prevalent during Physics practical. Prevalent errors in Chemistry practical ranged from personal errors to instrumental, observation, systematic, random, calculation, graph and errors in drawing. as regards biology practical, nearly all the errors are prevalent during practical except random and calculation errors. Therefore, errors commonly committed by students during practical which cut across the three core-fields of science include Personal errors, Instrumental errors, Observation errors, Systematic errors, Graph errors and Errors in drawing. This is in line with the findings of past researchers such as Nelkon (2000); Raymond (2011); Owolabi (2013); Gierlinski (2015) and Boundless (2016). For instance, Nelkon (2000) observed that personal errors such as imperfection of students' sense organs, breaking of apparatus due to phobia for practical examination among others are common occurrences during practical. In the same vein, Owolabi (2013) agreed that there are an endless number of potential mistakes in laboratory work, but some of the most common include observational errors, error due to parallax, systematic errors, random errors, error in drawing and error in graph among others. In addition, Gierlinski (2015) assert that random errors can be traceable to reading, sampling and counting errors. Also, Boundless (2016) found out that systematic errors are common during science practical because most of the experimenters do not know how to use apparatus properly. On the contrary, environmental errors which appear not to be prevalent across the three core-field of science (Physics, Chemistry and Biology) were among the three categories of common errors in science practical according to Assur and Filator in Bandede and Owolabi (2009).

Findings from the study also revealed that there was significant difference in the errors committed by students in Physics, Chemistry and Biology Practical as perceived by male and female science teachers. This corroborates the findings of Ogunleye and Babajide (2011) that science subjects are given masculine outlook by many educationists. This is in support of Oluwatelure (2015) that male find it less difficult in science to identify problem, gather information about the problem, formulate tentative statements, experiment, observe, interpret and make generalizations than the females. In relation to this, Ekwu (2016) submitted that gender has great impact on the effectiveness of teachers. Olu-Ajayi (2017) affirmed that there is a significant influence of teachers' gender on pupils' learning of science. On the contrary, Kolawole and Popoola (2011), Azman, et al (2018) affirmed that academic achievement is free of gender.

Conclusion

Considering the findings of this study, it was concluded that science practical activities in senior secondary schools were associated with different forms of errors with its negative effect on the performance of students in science subjects in both internal and external examinations. It was also concluded that perception of errors committed by science students varied with teachers' gender.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, it was recommended that:

1. The Government in conjunction with the State Ministry of Education should organize appropriate training through workshops, conferences and seminars for science teachers to enhance professional competencies in their jobs. This will enable them to inculcate in their students, the right attitude towards science which could further reduce the rate at which they commit errors during practical.
2. Science teachers should ensure that sufficient time for practical classes is accommodated on the school time table on weekly basis and pay more attention to the individual student in the practical classes so as to help them develop interest in the mastery of science practical content which could help to reduce errors.

References

- Aina, J.K. (2013). Importance of Science Education to National Development and Problems Militating Against Its Development. *American Journal of Education Research*, 1(7), 225-229
- Aina, J.K & Ayodele, M.O. (2018). The Decline in Science Students' Enrolment in Nigerian Colleges of Education: Causes and Remedies. *International Journal of Education and Practice*, 6(4), 167-178
- Ajayi, L.F. (2016). Effects of Collaborative learning on Sex, School location and Attitude Towards Chemistry among secondary school students in Nigeria. *Journal of Research in Science Education*, 1(1), 180-189.
- Allchin, D. (2000, February). "To Err is Science". A Paper presented at American Association for the Advancement of Science. Washington D.C.

- Aniodoh, H.C.O. & Egbo, J.J. (2013). Effect of Gender and Students' Achievement in Chemistry using Inquire Role Instructional Model. *Journal of Educational and Social Research*, 3(6)
- Arokoyu, A.A. & Charles-Ogan, G.I. (2017). Availability and utilisation of laboratory kits for practical teaching of mathematics in Chemistry. *American Journal of mathematics and statistics*, 7(4), 160-165
- Azman, N.Nor, Kamrudin, M.F, Ong, S.I & Maaulot, N. (2018). Gender Difference in Biology Academic Performance among Foundation Students of PERMATApinta @ National Gifted Center. *International Journal of Business, Human and Social Sciences*, 12(10), 1458-1464
- Bak, H.J. (2010). Education and Public attitudes toward Science: Implications for the "Deficit Model" of education and support for Science and technology.
- Bandele, S.O. & Owolabi, O.T. (2009). Effect of Error Correcting Instructional Package (ECIP) on Physics Practical Lessons in Nigeria Secondary Schools. *Journal of Science Education*, 10(1), 47.
- Boundless. (2016, August). "Accuracy, Precision, and Error." Boundless Chemistry Boundless. Retrieved August 21st, 2017, from <http://www.boundless.com/chemistry/textbooks/boundless-chemistry-textbook/introduction-to-chemistry-1/measurement-uncertainty-30/accuracy-precision-and-error-1990-3706/>
- Ekwu, M.G. (2016). *Science Teachers' Awareness and Use of Innovative Teaching Strategies in Secondary School Science in Ekiti State Nigeria*. Unpublished M.Ed Thesis. Ekiti State University, Ado Ekiti.
- Emmanuel, B.(2013). The Place of Nigeria Certificate in Education Chemistry Teachers in UBE Basic Science Programme. Science Teachers Association of Nigeria (STAN), 54th Annual conference proceedings, 171-181
- Gierlinski, M. (2015). *Understanding statistical error: a primer for biologists*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Gracy, A. (2016). *Learner Centered Education*. New Delhi: Random Publications
- Kolawole, E.B. & Popoola, A.A. (2011). Four Ability Process Dimension (4APD) as a Function of Improving Teaching and Learning of Basic Mathematics in Ekiti State Secondary Schools. *ABACUS: Journal of Mathematics Association of Nigeria*, 36(1), 113-118
- Liswaniso, L. J. (2019). An Investigation into the Teaching of Biology and Physical Science Practical Works in Senior Secondary Schools in Zambezi Region, Namibia. Published Thesis

- Nelkon, M. (2000). *Principle of Physics*. CSS Bookshops and Hart-Davis Educational (Nig) Ltd.
- Nzewi, U.M. (2008). Practical approach to the effective of ecological concepts for sustainable development. *Science Teachers' Association of Nigeria (STAN) Biology Panel 2008 series*, 1-6
- Ogunleye, B.O. & Adepeju, O.F (2011). Everyday Phenomena in Physics Education: Impact on male and female students' achievement, attitude and practical skills in urban and pre-urban setting in Nigeria. *Pakistan Journal of Social Sciences*, 8(6), 316-324
- Ogunleye, B.O. & Babajide, V.F.T. (2011). Commitment to Science and Gender as Determinants of Students Achievement and Practical Skills in Physics. *Journal of Science Teachers Association of Nigeria*.
- Olu-ajayi, F.E. (2017). Influence of Teachers' Gender on Primary School Pupils Attitude Towards Science Learning. *Journal of Current Discourse and Research*, 5(1), 74-78.
- Oluwatelure, T.A. (2015). Gender Difference in Achievement and attitude of Public Secondary School students towards science. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 6(2)
- Owolabi, O.T. (2003). *Design and Validation of Error Correcting Instructional Package (ECIP) for Secondary School Physics Practical*. Unpublished Doctoral Thesis. University of Ado Ekiti, Nigeria.
- Owolabi, O.T. (2007). Designing a package to minimize Errors in Physics Practical lessons in Nigeria Secondary Schools. *Research Journal of Applied Sciences*, 2(12), 1235-1238
- Owolabi, O.T. (2013). Relative and Interaction Effects of Errors in Physics Practical. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*. 1(3), 156-162.
- Raymond, E.D.F. (2011). *Surveying Theory and Practice*. New York: Mc Graw Hill Publisher Company.

Cite this article:

Author(s), JEGEDE Samuel Akingbade (Ph.D), OTOIDE Titilayo Folayemi, (2021). "Prevalent Errors in Senior Secondary School Science Practical as Perceived by Science Teachers in Ekiti State, Nigeria". **Name of the Journal:** International Journal of Academic Research in Business, Arts and Science, (IJARBAS.COM), P, 35-49. **DOI:** <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5015307> , Special Issue: 6, Vol.: 3, Article: 3, Month: June, Year: 2021. Retrieved from <https://www.ijarbas.com/all-issues/>

Published by

AND

ThoughtWares Consulting & Multi Services International (TWCMSI)

